

Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat (in English)

Theme: Energy, European Research Area and SSH Aspects

Bärbel EPP

Solrico Research Agency

Moderator: Pinar Derin Güre

Live Seminar Time and Date: 12:00-13:00 (Turkish time / GMT + 3)

Friday, May 13, 2022

Register at: <https://forms.gle/2isj1N2iDiBji1cf7>

Moderation: Assoc. Prof. Dr. Pinar Derin Güre

Registration for live seminar closes at 20:00, Thursday, 12 May 2022: To receive the link to the live seminar you must register by 20:00, Thursday 12 May 2022.

Abstract: Solrico has teamed up with IRENA for collecting cost data of a representative number of realised commercial and industrial (C&I) solar heat projects commissioned between 2010 and 2020 in the major solar heat markets worldwide. The aim was to add solar heat for the first time in IRENA's flagship publication Renewable Power Generation Costs in June 2021. The analysis results in cost charts either in total installed costs (USD/kW) or Levelized Cost of Heat (USD/kWh). The final results of the cost analysis show impressive cost reductions over time in selected markets. The European large-scale plants also have achieved great economies of scale.

Speaker:

Bärbel Epp is the founder and managing director of the German market research agency Solrico. She is responsible for the international newsletter on the web portal www.solarthermalworld.org, reporting exclusively about market and technology trends in the solar heating and cooling sector globally. Solrico also created the first online World Map of SHIP suppliers (SHIP = Solar Heat for Industrial Processes) see <http://www.solar-payback.com/suppliers> and carries out annual surveys among the around 70 companies listed on the world map annually. Since seven years Bärbel Epp is author of the SHC chapter of the annual Global Status Report on Renewables published by REN21. Further information: www.solrico.com

About SolarTwins-TEKPOL Seminars: The path to a prosperous, sustainable, and secure Turkey includes a Clean Energy Transition (CET) and Green Economy Transition (GET). Many of the largest challenges to be solved to realize these transitions lie at the intersection of technology and policy. Some of these challenges are unique to a specific technology, while others are cross-cutting challenges that underpin the competitiveness of Turkey's Research and Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. This SolarTwins-TEKPOL Pizza Seminar series aims to provide a scientific forum to increase awareness of these challenges and contribute to the co-creation of solutions to overcome these challenges. This series is designed as a part of SolarTwins Project Joint Research Line 9: Social Aspects of Sustainable Energy Transitions

About SolarTwins: SolarTwins is a European Union Horizon 2020 (H2020) project coordinated by ODTÜ-GÜNAM through METU with CIEMAT-PSA (Spain) and DLR (Germany) as partners. The objectives of the SolarTwins project are to

1. Step-up the scientific excellence of the Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) Research Division ODAK of ODTÜ-GÜNAM through capacity building activities in collaboration with the globally leading CST institutions CIEMAT-PSA and DLR.
2. Strengthen METU, ODTÜ-GÜNAM, and Turkey's horizontal Research and Innovation (R&I) Capacities.

About METU TEKPOL: Science and Technology Policy Studies (STPS) program was founded in 1997 at the Middle East Technical University with the explicit objective to supply science and technology policy related human capital for the government bodies, agencies and other related organizations and to conduct research in science, technology and innovation policy issues. It has organic relations with the Research Center for Science and Technology Policies. Education and research elements integrate under METU-TEKPOL. TEKPOL is the only academic unit in Turkey that concurrently coordinates education and research activities. It operates M.Sc. and Ph.D. programs in science technology policy studies at the Graduate School of Social Sciences. TEKPOL also conducts interdisciplinary research on science and technology policy issues with the aim of addressing societal challenges.

PROGRAMME:

Date	Speaker, Institution	Seminar Title
15 April 2022	Arda MEVLÜTOĞLU, Kubilay YILDIRIM and Semih AKÇOMAK	TOGG and Beyond (in Turkish) – Panel
22 April 2022	Onur Çağdaş ARTANTAŞ	Promotion of Green Electricity: Legal and Political Perspectives (in Turkish)
29 April 2022	Serdar TÜRKELİ	Technological change and non-intervention, novel indicators and non-measurement (in Turkish)
13 May 2022	Barbel EPP	Cost Trends for Commercial and Industrial Solar Heat
20 May 2022	Pınar DERİN GÜRE	Gender and social sciences involvement in technology development projects in energy (in Turkish)
27 May 2022	Şuhnaz YILMAZ ÖZBAĞCI	Energy Security Challenges: Assessing Turkey's Role in Changing Regional Dynamics (in Turkish)
3 June 2022	Derek BAKER	ODAKTR: Concentrating Solar Thermal (CST) as a key enabling technology for Turkey's Clean Energy Transition.
10 June 2022	Christian OLTRA	Introducing SSH aspects of Energy Transitions
17 June 2022	Sara Banu AKKAŞ and Zelal ÖZDEMİR	METU in New European Research Area (in Turkish)
24 June 2022	Seven AĞIR	AgroPV Potential, Opportunities and Barriers in Turkey: A Preliminary Evaluation From Social Sciences Perspective (in Turkish)

Contact: Yelda ERDEN TOPAL
yeldae@metu.edu.tr

ERKAN ERDİL
erdil@metu.edu.tr

Derek K. BAKER
dbaker@metu.edu.tr

SolarTwins has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 856619.